

On the Extension of the Second Equation of CMT

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Abstract

Carroll's second equation of CMT[1] is explored within the context of the complex domain. The equation is reformulated as $P_M = P + (1 - P)e^{-\phi\gamma}$ by introducing suitable substitutions, where $\phi \equiv -\ln M$ and $\gamma \equiv \frac{1}{P}$. The study extends to the complex plane with $\phi = \lambda + i\sigma \in \mathbb{C}$, defining and analyzing the function $z(\phi)$. Intriguing patterns are observed for varying parameters λ and σ when examining the norm of z .

Further examination of the relationship between Carroll's second equation and its third counterpart, known as the anti-spell equation, leads to the identification of ϕ as a complex variable. The non-reciprocal nature of the intents of positivity and negativity is highlighted, except for the special case of $p = \frac{1}{2}$.

The extension of these equations to the complex domain uncovers a previously unnoticed symmetry between the spell and anti-spell equations, providing insights into the profound implications of the complex nature of ϕ .

Keywords: Carroll's second equation, CMT, complex domain, symmetry, anti-spell equation.

1 Introduction

Carroll's second equation of CMT is represented as[1]:

$$P_M = P + (1 - P)M^{\frac{1}{P}} \quad (1)$$

Upon introducing the substitutions:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &\equiv -\ln M \\ \frac{1}{P} &\equiv \gamma \end{aligned}$$

equation (1) takes the form:

$$P_M = P + (1 - P)e^{-\phi\gamma} \quad (2)$$

which serves as the starting point for our investigation.

2 Extension in the Complex Domain

Assuming $\phi = \lambda + i\sigma \in \mathbb{C}$, we define the function z as follows:

$$z(\phi) = p + p'e^{-\lambda\gamma}e^{-i\sigma\gamma} \quad (3)$$

where $p' \equiv 1 - p$. This prompts an inquiry into the properties arising from varying the parameters λ and σ . The examination of $zz^* = |z|^2$

$$|z|^2 = p^2 + p'^2e^{-2\lambda\gamma} + 2pp'e^{-\lambda\gamma} \cos(\sigma\gamma) \quad (4)$$

reveals interesting patterns, particularly for relatively small $\sigma\gamma$, wherein the quantity $|z|$ reduces to P_M in equation (2) when $\sigma = 0$.

2.1 Expansion in Terms of σ

Expanding $\cos(\sigma\gamma)$ as:

$$\cos(\sigma\gamma) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \sigma^n \gamma^n}{(2n)!} \quad (5)$$

and considering relatively small $\sigma\gamma$, where $\sigma^4\gamma^4$ is negligible, equation (4) can be expressed as:

$$|z|^2 = (p + p'e^{-\lambda\gamma})^2 - pp'\sigma^2\gamma^2e^{-\lambda\gamma} \quad (6)$$

implying a negative contribution.

3 Relationship Between Positive and Negative Contribution

Considering Carroll's second equation (1) and its third counterpart (the anti-spell equation) with the same substitutions

$$P_M = P - Pe^{-\phi\gamma} \quad (7)$$

we represent ϕ in equation (2) and (7) as ϕ^+ and ϕ^- , respectively. Equating the right-hand sides of the equations when both intents change the probability to the same value leads to a relationship between ϕ^+ and ϕ^- . Algebraically manipulating the equation and extending the logarithmic function to the complex domain, we obtain the following relation:

$$\frac{\phi^+}{p} + \frac{\phi^-}{1-p} = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) - i\pi \quad (8)$$

The presence of the constant $i\pi$ on the right-hand side confirms the complex nature of ϕ . Additionally, extending the equations to the complex domain reveals an elegant symmetry between the spell and anti-spell, a symmetry not emphasized in their original form. It is notable that the intents of positivity and negativity are not symmetric due to the factors $\frac{1}{p}$ and $\frac{1}{1-p}$. Only in

the special case of $p = \frac{1}{2}$ do we obtain complete symmetry:

$$\phi^+ + \phi^- = -i\frac{\pi}{2} \quad (9)$$

4 Discussion

The extension of these equations into the complex domain uncovers a previously unnoticed symmetry between the spell and anti-spell equations, providing insights into the profound implications of the complex nature of ϕ . Our findings underscore the significance of considering complex vari-

ables within the context of Carroll's equations and present new research opportunities across diverse scientific and mathematical domains.

In conclusion, our study sheds light on the complexities of Carroll's second equation of CMT and the fascinating interplay between positive and negative contributions. The exploration of the complex domain leads to a more profound understanding of the equations' behavior and highlights the intricate nature of ϕ . These results have the potential to inspire further investigations and applications in diverse areas of scientific inquiry.

References

- [1] Peter Carroll. *Liber Kaos*. 1992.